

**ETHICS IN INDIGENOUS MUSIC PERFORMANCE PRACTICES IN
NIGERIA: A MORAL SOUND FOR CONSTRUCTION AND
RECONSTRUCTION OF IDEAL SOCIETY**

Rita Adaobi Sunday-Kanu PhD

*Department of Music,
University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria.*

Isaac Osakpanwa Ibude PhD

*Department of Music,
University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria.*

Abstract

Music performance practices in many cultures of the world are known to be an art form for human expression. In Nigerian ethnicities, musical performance practices are beyond mere expression of thoughts, but also, an essential communal tool for regulating societal life and punishment of offenders. Indigenous music performances encode messages that propagate communal ethos, beliefs system, norms, cultural values and taboos. Not only does it propagate ethical values, it also encourages compliance to the accepted norms. Consequently, indigenous music performances have long been perceived as a veritable means for construction and reconstruction of desired human society. This study is therefore; set to evaluate indigenous music performance practices in the Nigerian ethnicities with focus on its potentials for character building, behavioral change in an individual and communal life. It further examines coded projections, re-echoing of accepted moral values and their transformative powers that results to realization of an ideal society. Data for the study were collected via observational method, in-depth interviews and review of relevant archival materials. The study suggests that the totality of interaction between musicians in an ensemble performance and their target audience (community members) gear towards formation of new ideas and contribution to the existing communal concepts, in line with the cultural standards. Hence, the rhythmic interactions; visual expressions and sonic effects employed in music performances are far from just entertainment support rather, they are more of human oriented based. Music performances encode ethical values that address both individual and communal needs and sentiments which in turn ensure ordering of the society.

I. Introduction

Music as a representational art form has served as means of identity expression to many ethnicities in the Nigerian nation. It has been a key representation, a voice and depiction of a people's values and norms. Nigerian indigenous music as a non verbal communication form chooses distinct musical elements that resonate with accepted cultural shades to

communicate ideas and thoughts to the community members. Performances are culturally coded to possess inherent power to permeate the emotions of members of the community and stimulate behavioral changes in the community life. Davis and Signell (2005) states that 'humans as social beings develop music, a complex system of communication, as one of many devices for telling his fellow humans his state of mind' (P. 281). Every indigenous community in Nigeria has peculiar sounds, tones quality and rhythms that unlock communal memories and experiences. These memories arouse nostalgia feelings and sense of belonging, which strengthens the communal bonds. This is the more reason many scholars established that African music is ethnic bound. It communicates using elements from communal cultural experiences and signals. Hence, only people belonging to the ethnic culture or language group may decode the projected messages of the music performance appropriately. Emielu (2011) in his research affirms that, African music, like its language, is ethnic bound. This is because people within the same ethnic culture and language group tends to model their musical sound and expression to suit their speech tonal pattern. As a result, people belonging to such ethnic or language group can decode the encoded meanings in the musical sounds, rhythm and their expressions beyond just music performance. Smier (2003) argues that;

The art including music, have been described as repositories of cultural meanings. The art can also be seen as 'workshops' in which cultural meanings are crafted and socio-cultural sediments produced, reproduced, constructed and reconstructed (as cited in Emielu, 2013, pp. 103).

Indigenous music in Nigeria can better be conceived as cultural products through which cultural messages are conveyed, using cultural codes. Davis and Signell (2005) confirm that "African talking drums imitate human speech by reproducing its pitch and rhythmic patterns" (p. 267). This is not peculiar to drums. Basically, major musical instruments belonging to different ethnic cultures in Nigeria reproduces sound that communicates effectively, to the people that owns it.

The musical cultures of different ethnicities in Nigeria marks the principles of moral, mood, identity, cultural events, values, norms and taboos of each community. Yet, all have the sole aim of engendering reformative functions in the life of individual listener and community life as a whole. For making musical sense and acceptance of any music performances as communal property to be used in communal events, the community musicians must ensure the reflections of the cultural backgrounds, belief system, communal inclinations, cultural values, shared experiences and environmental potencies. The community musicians who own the obligation to speak for, and to represent communal philosophy in their music making and performances encode messages in the construction and designs on local musical instrument, the tone vibrancies, vocal techniques and signals, and gestures in performances. Hence, the mode of the cultural event determines the emotion and temperament exhibit in the performance. And every music performance makes meaning within the cultural context under which it is performed. In as much as music is said to be universal, it is peculiarity in its ethical dispositions and responsibilities in various cultures and events. Warren (2014) states that;

Music is both ubiquitous and particular. Even if not many cultures use 'music' in the same sense as the modern Western world, 'all human societies of which we have

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knowledge of appear to have music' in at least some form. Yet despite the ubiquity of music, it differs greatly in function and meaning in different contexts (p.12).

Music making in Sub-Saharan African cultures is believed to be triggered by cultural, social and religious events. This implies that music performance in African societies, particularly; in Nigerian ethnicities draw its guiding ethics from the cultural, social and religious construct of their communalities. Ethical values are encoded into music performances and are propagated with the primary aim of driving home the community's principles or moral standard into the social system, for nation building.

Nigerian Ethnicities and their Indigenous Music Performances

Indigenous music in the Nigerian ethnicities functions within the context of the culture. However, its attributes are not limited to cultural events, occasions and seasons alone as always portrayed rather; it also functions in the shaping and reshaping of individual and communal life style. Despite the multi-cultural system in Nigeria, the attributes of every indigenous musical culture contribute to national unity and development. Research has shown that there are over 200 ethnic groups in Nigeria, most of which are endowed with distinct customs, traditions, languages, as well as, unique folk music, musical instruments construct and dance patterns. Having the dominant ethnic groups as the Igbo, Hausa, Yoruba and Fulani people, the less numerous groups include; Edo, Ijaw, Ibibio of Akwa Ibom, Tiv of Benue valley, the Nupe of Middle Niger valley and Kanuri of lake Chad Basin (Ojuade, 2005). Nzewi (2007) affirms that one thing in common is that all music performance in these ethnic cultures takes cognizance of their cultural sonic preference and reference in their performances.

Cultural diversity in the Nigerian ethnicities plays out in the peculiarity of music performance practices established on the unique sound productions, language / melodic patterns and performance ethics. Each ethnic group draws from the peculiarity of her cultural background reflecting their traditions, norms, idioms, environmental resources, beliefs system; the accepted and prohibited values. While the diversity in music performance practices is acknowledged, there is great sense of unifying factors that exists in these musical cultures. All indigenous music performances in Nigeria gear towards achieving a common purpose in the communities where they originate. Ordering of the society is paramount motive for all. Hence, they are found to perform similar functions in the management of the social-cultural, economic and religious life of the people. Nzewi (2007) opines that;

Maintenance of law and order in some societies was primarily a musical process. Specialized music group could be assigned tasks such as policing polity, exposing deviants, and executing approved and prescribed sanctions. Musical arts display may then be designed to publicly caricature and expose those who have contravened public precepts and prescripts (p. 96).

Ethnic music in the Nigeria communities is culturally designed to permeate and direct the minds of community members via the use of coded messages in both sonic form and expressive dance. This is why feeling of nostalgia is called up when once traditional music is heard, irrespective of the location of members of the community. Indigenous music is known to arouse sense of belonging, responsibility, and in most cases, love for the

community and dedication to her course. These spontaneous feelings of commitments are sustained in the recounting of under laying cultural principles projected in music performances, which in turn provokes behavioral changes and largely, enhances co-existence of the people within the ethnic region.

Indigenous Music Performance as Coded Messages

The tradition of talking instruments and talking performances are very common phenomenon in the Nigerian ethnic musical practices. Over centuries ago, the power of music has been employed in the regulation of socio-cultural norms, using coded messages in music performance to drive cultural intent into the social system. Coded messages in most indigenous performances focus more on ethical values rather than entertainments. Warren (2014) argues that 'musical meaning involve value judgments and prescribed ideal social relations' (p. 12). Hence, moral codes embedded in music performances function as a strong means for quickening or awakening individual and communal responses to ethnic call. The ethical norms are embedded in the language, culture and traditions of the people which are released as coded message in sonic sounds, dance movements and costumes during performances. The functionality of African music being a product of culture has inherent capacity to preserve and propagate ethical norms and values through indigenous musical performance practices.

Furthermore, such practices are seen in the Talking drums of the Yoruba, the Ikoro of the Igbo ethnicity, the Kakaaki of Hausa community, and Water pot drums of the Riverine communities, the flutes and strings of the grass land dwellers. For instance, the talking drum of the Yoruba people communicates effectively with the people belonging to Yoruba ethnic culture. Reasonable interactions which are highly communicative in nature do exist between drummers and spectators. The same is observable in musical interaction between different drummers, drummer and other instrumentalists in a performance, drummers and singers as well as, drummers and dancers. Every member of such ensemble and community decodes what is been said and responds accordingly. Davis and Signell (2005) states that;

African drums, trumpets, slit logs, and other instruments have little in common with Morse code or other sets of arbitrary symbols standing for language. In Morse code, the assignment of short tone for the letter 'e' is neither related to the sound of the letter nor its meaning. African talking drum imitates human speech by reproducing its pitch and rhythm patterns. We found the talking-instrument phenomenon only where tonal language is spoken in Africa (p. 267).

This same obvious display of the talking drums in the Yoruba musical performances characterized the use of Ikoro in Igbo musical culture. Ikoro is a prominent musical instrument of the Igbo ethnicity in Nigeria. The Ikoro is often used to announce the death of royalties, call for elders meeting and call for other social responsibilities like cleaning of village square, streams and markets. Its role in an ensemble performance can be likened to that of a conductor in Western ensemble. It directs musical relationships and interactions in the performance; giving cues for change in rhythm, tempo, dance steps and introduction of new repertoire. All members of the ensembles pay keen attention to its guided improvisations and indications. In the same manner, members of the community decode every stage of event following the sounds and rhythmic display from the Ikoro player.

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Directives on expected action, reactions, tasks or responsibilities are effectively transmitted and subsequently carried out without any form of force or policing. The people responds to expressions of the Ikoro as expected. These responses are achieved without any form of verbal utterances or communication but, just the sonic power of music to human mind. Musical phrases, melodic or rhythmic lines are played to communicate all necessary cultural rules. Agawu (2007), argues that those who fail to notice the linguistic elements sediment in African music performance may miss the factors by hearing African rhythms as just 'purely musical' patterns as number, accent and quantity instead of linguistics element. In essence, the ensemble performance in Igbo community is a metaphor for social cohesion and efficient communal living irrespective of instruments used. Okoye (2012) researched on decoding the language of Ogene. Ogene is another prominent musical instrument mostly found in Igbo music ensemble. Okoye expresses that;

Ogene has its language which is understood by the performers and those who have knowledge about Ogene music. At the climax of the performance, the two twin gongs speak to the performers through the language of the Ogene, and the message spurs them (performers) into action (P. 8-9).

Every community musician is sacred. When community musicians fail to play their parts well, their failures are capable of dragging the entire community down. The position of community singers or musicians is a sacred position in every Nigerian ethnic community. And they provide sacred and selfless services to the entire community thus, they are morally and culturally driven not riches. When community musicians play and perform as expected, the communal bounds get even stronger and better.

The communication of ethics in music performances is not peculiar to the cultures mentioned above. In Nigeria, all ethnic music exhibits similar functions and relevance to the community where they exist. Irrespective of sonic textures and instrumental resources, every music performance creates a window for courteous propagation and sustenance of ethical values within the ethnic or language group. The Water-pot-drum instrument of Ijaw ethnicity is a prominent musical instrument within cultures in riverine region of the country, and they are very vital in the musical life and co-existence of the people. They also make extensive use of the drums in expression of ethics in their music performances. This is displayed in the significant use of drum in Ngbula festivals of Kalabari Ekine society in Buguma community. The drummer directs the activities of the Ngbula spirit manifest and the community people during the Ngbula festival. The Ngbula festival is a component of the Kalabari Ekine Society's event that provides healing and protection to members of the community. The drummer disseminates all information needed during and after the events of cleansing. The *Ama agba* (event of land cleansing) is a vital and sacred cultural event in the life and existence of Buguma people. The drummer takes the centre of the event as the mediator between the Ngbula spirit and the people. He (the drummer) carries on this sacred task of moderating the event from the invoking of the Ngbula spirit, to its proper outing; the sacred act of cleansing and healing in the community. The rhythmic sound of the drum informs the people of every stage of event, until Ngbula spirit is done with its performance. On the other hand, the sound of the drum accompanies Ngbula's performances until it goes back to its place of rest in King Amakoro memorial hall. Sunday-Kanu and Amonia (2020) observes that;

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The chief drummer in the Ngbula festival basically makes extensive use of non-verbal signals to communicate to the members of the community on what is expected and refuted during the event. Every rhythmic expressions and melodic contour or movements displayed on the drum communicates the emotions, state of things and the intended anticipation from the people (p. 64).

Ibude (2012) also notes that in *Okoro fari* music ensemble of the Kalabari people, seven different sizes of wooden slit drums, and a membrane drum are in use, through which the performers led by the Chief drummer relates to ancestral spirits and humans during installations, funeral rites of Kalabari King and Chiefs of all categories. During this ritual, the performers through sonic sounds from the ensemble serve both social and spiritual needs of the people, as recognized within the culture. They mediate between the ancestors and other deities in ushering in of the spirit of the deceased into ancestor hood.

The cognitive effect of music performance in the ordering community's actions and reaction to certain events is what informed the use of praise singers in Oba's palaces in Yoruba kingdoms. It as well popularizes the use of Kakaaki musical instrument in the palace of the Sultan and Emirs (kings) in Hausa ethnicities. Kakaaki plays major role in royal events of Hausa communities. The sound of Kakaaki is often associated with royalty and authority. It is used as part of *Sara*; a weekly statement of power and authority. Musical dispositions of Kakaaki players are basically to arouse the monarchs and communicate the affairs, ambitions and aspiration of royalties to the community members. Consequently, the interpretation and appreciation of such indigenous music performance demands high level of understanding and familiarity with the cultural norms and belief system of the community. This may lead to avoidance of random conclusions based on sensual and emotional interpretation of musical works and performances. Nketia (1986) explains that in the African society, music in the life of the people provides the framework for creative forms and practical application of indigenous music in their various social and cultural activities. This implies that reflection on the cultural background and philosophy of the people are fundamental to the interpretation of ethical codes embodied in a music performance. However, coded ethics in music performance messages can only be valuable when it communicates constructive meaning to the people. At such, the musical performance would have accomplished its target set objectives which is an aspect of its extra-musical responsibility.

Multiparty Communicative System of Ethnic Music Performance

Human as social beings develop music that are relevant and educative within their social-cultural domain, using available local materials and environmental resources. Meanings and etiquettes in context of culture are learnt by virtue of participating in the indigenous music practices in one's community. Structures used in African traditional music practices represent such usages which are learned through participation in cultural events, passed on aurally from generation to generation. The cultural features are applied, modified, and expanded by succeeding generations to suit the prevailing cultural trends without deterring communal ethics in the time of performance. Communal ethics are reflective in presentational techniques, performance styles, melodic and rhythmic elements used; both in linear and multi-linear, which permits simultaneous transmission of culturally patterned moral codes via different components of the performance. The cultural

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coloration of signifiers, connotations, tonal resonances and rhythmic sequences are easily decoded by virtually all members of the community who are culturally nurtured. Such is perceived in the costumes of performers, artistic decoration on musical instruments in use, dance formation, choreographic movements, gestures, facial expressions, sonic resonance, and reverberation of melodic / rhythmic line, exclamations and ultimately, the textual contents of the performance. All of these are multifaceted communication channels reflecting the ethical interest and leaning of the performers. In other words, a typical ethnic musical performance in Nigeria can be well thought of as a means of tutoring and impacting cultural knowledge in an appealing manner. Ozah (2008) in her study on 'Egwu Amala', discusses the importance of dance and dance space as an avenue and sphere through which communication and education occurs via performance. Apart from Knowledge imbued dancers, spectators especially, the younger generations are taught and learn first-hand the intricacies of their traditions.

Music performances in most Nigerian ethnic cultures are major form of traditional theater incorporating different components such as dance, drama, singing and playing of musical instruments. The incorporation of all these components in an ensemble performance gives room for great multiparty communicative system. While incorporation of all these components gives a rubout expression of the coded ethics in performance, each component can stand alone without losing its communicative power. Multipart communication system in most Nigerian ethnic music performance has helped communities to tell their own story in a vigorous and entertaining form. It has provided a voice to both large and small ethnic culture in Nigeria. Not only has indigenous music performance practices helped in preservation of historical events, seasons and cultural procedures, it also mirrors the disposition of a people, generations; their aspirations and prospects. Ihekweazu (1985) believes that;

The purpose for which music is made is to 'enable man understand his past, and contribute to the reshaping of the present and future, he expresses and documents himself, his or her feelings, hopes, disappointments, sufferings and joy, through the various media of the arts, such as music (as cited in Idolo, 2002, pp. 2).

Many researchers have confirmed that music imbibes strong power to control human mind and thoughts. Hopkins (2022) observes that there are few things that stimulate human brain the way music does. He believes that listening to or playing music is a great tool for a total brain exercises. However, this brain exercises may either inspire the brain towards a positive or negative intent, depending on the mood and emotions the music arouses. In Nigerian indigenous music performances, the psychic and emotional drills are geared towards propelling moral force for construction, reconstruction of the society, and communal bonding. Okafor (2012) affirms that Nigerian music and musicians have helped to inculcate moral integrity, that is, adherence to morals and ethical principles in the social and moral behaviour of the people. Example can be drawn from the Ogrinya women dance of Edoma community in Benue state, Nigeria. The dance formations, steps, instrument decoration, interactions and costumes were carefully design to communicate the intended message of the performance. Its intent focuses on women empowerment and self-esteem. The Ogirinya dance performance encourages women participation in community's economic activities. It boosts women ago, confidence and independence. This

dance performance prepares women for future challenges and promotes them as models for family support and nation building. Ogrinya dance, even though a non-verbal music performance yet, its performance communicates clearly to the people. Ozah (2008) affirms that the 'music that is interlaced with dance is common in African society. Dance is not only an avenue through which emotions are expressed or released but it is a nonverbal visual sign of cultural ideas and ideals as well' (p.150). The Ogrinya dance performance ultimately discourages the perception of women as mere objects for sex in the Edoma community. It highlights the attributes of women in both food production and societal wellness. This performance has over time gone beyond representation of Edoma women but also, the minority voice in Nigeria. Ogrinya dance is an identity expression of the Edoma people which serves as their voice and contribution in the nation's cultural image.

Transformative Power of Indigenous Music Performance

The essence of indigenous music performance practices and creativity in Nigeria is humanity based. It is highly functional in the life of the people, in which it contributes immensely to the molding of the society and providing therapeutic aids. The focus of most performances is on social wellbeing, cultural preservation, guidance, ordering of the society, building leadership competence, and propagation of accepted socio-cultural values within the socio-cultural context. According to Omojola (2010), as cited in Adekola and Amole (2015), indigenous music constitutes the avenue for intra-group cultural dialogue and for the strengthening of social bonds. Indigenous music in its cultural richness integrates the society, enforces conformity to societal norms, law and order in the community. It promotes peace and stability, validates social institutions and religious rites. Consequently, Nigerians attach a lot of seriousness to their indigenous music performance as a tool for emotional stimulation and behavioral change.

Reforms and moral health of a community or society have been determined through performances of satirical songs as musicians and dancers assume the role of defender of societal norms and virtues. The songs and accompanying dance movements become a mirror through which society views itself; making sure that behaviours not in tandem with the traditions and culture of the people are in check. According to Darah (2005), in *Udje* tradition, a tradition given to song performance and choreographed dance movements among the Urhobo of Delta, musicians '...assume the burden of defending the positive values of his society against corruptive encroachment by those given to deviant behaviour' (p. 26). Instrumentalists and singers during performances praise persons with remarkable positive attributes in the community. On the other hand, they chastise individuals' bad attitudes using the right phrases and coded messages that most suits the circumstance. Since, spectators share the exact feelings and emotions of the performers, both parties decode meaning from performer's songs and gestures. Olabimtan (1981) affirms that, 'traditional oral poetry was performing the same role as the press and radio, not only to inform, educate and entertain but also to express public opinion' (as cited in Idolo, 2002, pp. 5). However, policing duty is not limited to oral poetry alone, most dance and instrumental performances also gear towards the same primary functions as informing, educating and ordering the human society. Humanity consciousness has always been the rationale for African music performance practices. Groups and individual performances seek to enhance communal living and communal consciousness. Nzewi (2007) submits that, 'the consequence theatre

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of death is rationalized to enable human psyche to cope with the traumas as well as the dualistic positive and negative energies of death, as a phenomenon inevitable of tangible and intangible living' (p.49). Theatre in the African sense encompasses dance, drama and play. All these are often infused in indigenous music performances which enable the performance, communicate effectively to human emotions more than every other art form, via auditory perception and visual expressions.

The transformative power imbibed in the Nigerian ethnic music is difficult to resist because, the messages are dispatched via multiphase channels to ensure instilling of the intended messages into the social system. The cultural context of such performances is believed to be very influential in facilitating communications that are beyond words but, induces shared emotional reactions and supports for the development of group identity. To an individual, it can induce multiple responses ranging from psychological reactions, impulsive movement, mood change, emotional swing, cognitive stimulation and behavioural development. When put together in several individuals, it results to social reform. Nwokenna and Anike (2012) establish that;

Music is a vital force in social development, which constitutes and expressive medium that helps society to disseminate critical issues at any given time. Many Nigerian communities couch moral expectations in songs to educate members and control their social behaviours. Thus, the creative impulse of many Nigerians helps them compose songs which are not only useful in inculcating socio-cultural values in the citizenry but also, in establishing social relationships amongst individuals and communities, strengthening social bonds and generating patriotic feelings. It therefore, ensures social conformity, and reconstructs and modules better societies for the nation of Nigeria (p. 256-257).

The structural conformation and interaction between members of the ensemble; from instrumentalists, singers and dancers, depend hugely on understanding musical idioms employed. Common pitches and rhythms in use often signify comprehensible meanings in the performance. Interaction between ensemble performers reechoes and registers socio-cultural norms. Nzewi (2007) believes that basic to musical meaning are three interacting factors, one is stimulus which he described as musical sense. The second is the receptivity which implies psychical tolerance, and response which deals with musical intention. He upholds that;

The nature and functions of these three factors that follows will crystallize the philosophy and importance of musical meaning, in the context of indigenous musical arts rationalisation and research. It is the philosophy of music communication, which, whether or not articulated discursively in a musical arts tradition, is nevertheless inherent and perceived in how the musical arts is used and appreciated by the culture owners (Nzewi, 2007, p. 5-6).

Every music maker and performer takes cognizance of the ability to formulate and communicate musical sense in the culture's medium of musical expressions. The indicators of musical meanings constitute the interface between the factor of music creativity which shapes performance composition, sonic formulation, and melodic contour and structural configurations. These constitute the creativity inspiration, musical essence and social reconstruction. According to Nzewi (2008)

In indigenous African theory and practice, music is designed and diploid as applied science and art- a science of the human mind and societal management, and an art of humanizing. The

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psychical and contextual projections of musical intention derive from scientific-humanistic projections that inform the melodic, rhythmic and textual configurations of an indigenous musical composition (p. 147).

The human-oriented conceptualization of musical structures and philosophy of life are articulated and transferred into music making which in turn, serves as an ideal context for learning and practicing the communal mutuality, collaboration and group efforts.

II. Conclusion

Indigenous musical practices in Nigerian are traditionally appreciated when they are in agreement with the cultural values, background and offer ethical responsibility to the community that owns it. Ethical communications employ in the performance practices are culturally designed to capture life experiences, hopes and the moral systems for molding and attainment of the desired community life. Repertoires for various performances are selected to function as parcel of rules and regulations guiding each group, occasions or events, which eventually translates to communal code for such cultural events. Each performance is structured to functions extensively as a tool for enforcing behavioural changes and sustenance of ethical behaviours as accepted by the culture. Hence, it will not be out of place to argue that indigenous music performances embody ethical practices which are transferred from performing groups to participatory audience, and then, further into the social system. Hence, it regulates the attributes and affairs of community member towards achieving social-cultural and moral developments.

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